

QSAR Applications to Toxicological Research and Risk Assessment

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Abstract

Safety assessment is an essential component of the regulatory acceptance of industrial chemicals. Humans are exposed to an ever-increasing number of chemicals, but only a fraction of these have been evaluated for potential risks to human health and the environment. Thus, both regulators and manufacturers need rapid and efficient approaches, such as New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) that help reduce the need for animal testing and address unmet need to modernize safety evaluation of chemical hazards. Computational models provide a fast and low-cost solution to obtain reliable predictions for the endpoint of concern when generated on high-quality curated data and properly validated. A major computational approach, quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSARs) have earned broad acceptance as a weight of evidence for assessing chemical toxicity. We will showcase our Pred-Skin sensitization web tool that incorporates multiple QSAR models developed with *in vitro*, *in chemico*, and *in vivo* (mice and human) data, integrated into a consensus naïve Bayes model that predicts human skin sensitization effect.